

PROTECTION OF BIG DATA THROUGH CONTRACTUAL CONSTRUCTS (SEPARATE TYPES OF OBLIGATIONS)

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Today, Big Data technologies are widely used in various fields, including medicine, finance, industry, education, and public administration. With the help of these technologies, large amounts of data are analyzed, and decision-making processes are carried out effectively. However, when working with Big Data, ensuring data security, confidentiality, and integrity remains a pressing issue.

Systems storing large amounts of data are at risk of cyberattacks and possible information leaks by internal staff. In this case, ensuring the confidentiality of information is recognized as the main issue. Also, storing data correctly and unchanged can lead to incorrect decision-making due to data corruption or manipulation. In such cases, the contractual approach to data protection is one of the most effective methods.

With the development of modern technologies, the concept of Big Data has reached a completely new level. The analysis of large volumes of data opened up new opportunities for enterprises, research centers, and government agencies. At the same time, issues of confidentiality and legal protection of information are becoming increasingly relevant. In particular, Non-disclosure agreement (NDA) There are serious debates among scientists and experts about how it works in the Big Data environment.

The development of Big Data technologies allows companies and research centers to develop business strategies using large amounts of information. At the same time, the confidentiality of personal data is becoming an increasingly important issue.

NDA's are often created to prevent the disclosure of confidential information to third parties. But since Big Data is constantly being updated and developed, there are ongoing debates about how to protect this data. For example, the effectiveness of data anonymization and encryption methods is still questionable.

Some scientists believe that strict restrictions on information protection can slow down innovation. For example, if large amounts of data are unusable due to NDA, significant research in the fields of medicine or artificial intelligence may be delayed.

Other researchers believe that the spread of personal data increases the risk of cybersecurity. For example, laws such as GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) are aimed at strengthening information protection in the European Union. The NDA serves as an important tool for protecting the interests of a company or individual.

A. Tojiboev emphasizes that this agreement is widely used in the activities of startups and notes that the Non-disclosure agreement (NDA) is widespread among the owner of the startup and the investor.

Considering the views of these scholars, in our opinion, the subject of the NDA agreement should be precisely *the implementation of necessary measures to prevent the dissemination or non-dissemination of any personal, commercial, or other information*. It is noted that all existing subjects of civil law participate as parties to the contract. In general, this agreement defines the obligations of the parties not to disclose information. Companies reduce the risk of data leakage by signing this document before sharing their data with third parties.

Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) are closely interconnected. Training AI models requires a large amount of data. However, due to NDA, access to some data may be limited, which can affect the quality and accuracy of analyses. For example, in the field of medicine, real patient data is necessary for the effectiveness of AI models, but their confidentiality is required.

Big Data technologies allow organizations to collect, store, and analyze vast amounts of data. However, these processes raise important legal issues regarding ensuring the confidentiality and security of personal data. In this regard, ***Data Processing Agreement (Data Processing Agreement - DPA)*** is of significant importance.

According to the analysis provided by WilmerHale, the DPA agreement is crucial for understanding and evaluating legal issues related to big data.

An article published in the Stanford Law Review highlighted the importance of the DPA agreement in managing and protecting personal data. The Washington University Open Scholarship also discussed the role of the DPA agreement to ensure confidentiality in the big data era¹.

According to the provisions of the GDPR, the DPA agreement defines the rights and obligations of the parties to protect personal data.

A DPA agreement is an agreement that defines the rights and obligations of the parties in the process of processing personal data, concluded between the owner (owner) of the information as a controller and the information processor.

This agreement is necessary to ensure the legal and safe processing of personal data².

Big data technologies require the processing of large volumes of personal data, which makes issues of confidentiality and security even more relevant. As parties to the DPA agreement, we can see that large giant corporations in the field of ICT usually act as data processors. In general, today in our country, organizations operating in the public and private sectors are considered parties to this agreement. For example, in the field of mobile communications (Beeline, Mobiuz, Ucell), in the field of the Internet (Uztelecom), and the Single Portal of Interactive Public Services of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Digital Government Project Management Center) my.gov.uz are information processors in accordance with the DPA agreement.

In our opinion, the DPA agreement is an important legal tool for ensuring the protection of personal data in the big data process. The DPA clearly defines the rights and obligations of the parties and ensures the safe and legitimate processing of personal data.

The development of the digital economy and Big Data technologies **increased the need for service level agreements (SLA)**. The SLA Agreement is a legal document that defines the conditions for the provision of services based on Big Data, the content of which determines the quality of service, the limits of liability, and the rights and obligations of the parties.

Scientists note that the SLA agreement plays an important role in Big Data relations not only in terms of service quality, but also in terms of data confidentiality and protection. These contracts serve as a legal basis between service providers and users.

The subject of the SLA agreement must clearly define the level of service provision, confidentiality and security of information, responsibility and dispute resolution, as well as the boundaries of responsibility between the service provider and the client. In our view, this agreement can be manifested through collaboration with service and intellectual property agreements (license agreement, copyright agreement, etc.) in our national legislation. Only a natural question arises about which institution's rules or methods are applied for liability for non-performance of obligations in this area.

If we define the SLA as a service agreement, in addition to the general provisions on the obligation, special provisions may apply. In particular, according to the rules for the provision of services, if the service provider

(contractor) does not fulfill the contract for the provision of paid services in full or to the proper extent, he is obliged to fully compensate the customer for the damage caused, but not more than twice the cost of the services specified in the contract. If this is done by business entities, enhanced civil liability is provided. These provisions are reflected in Article 706 of the Civil Code.³

If it is deemed necessary to apply the rules for the protection of intellectual property for the SLA agreement, the seizure of the objects by means of which the exclusive rights established by Article 1040 of the Civil Code were violated, as well as the material objects created as a result of such violation, can also be carried out by mandatory publication of information about the fact of the seizure or destruction and the inclusion in it of information about the ownership of the violated right. The main point for this is the reflection of the exclusive right to the data or database that is the subject of the SLA agreement⁴.

In general, according to the doctrine of contract law, the parties may conclude a mixed contract, which contains elements of various contracts. The rules on contracts constituting its components apply to the relations of the parties under such a contract. These provisions are reflected in Article 354 of the Civil Code.

In our opinion, it is advisable to apply the rules for the protection of intellectual property in both the provision of services and the SLA agreement.

Based on the principle of freedom of contract formation, the parties are allowed to conclude contracts not provided for by law. This rule is enshrined in Article 354 of the Civil Code. Thus, contracts such as NDA, DPA, and SLA are also considered a separate type of obligation, and the parties may conclude such contracts on the basis of information relations.

However, NDA, DPA, and SLA agreements (hereinafter - agreements in the information sphere), their content, or related provisions, are not yet encountered in either information legislation or civil legislation. In this case, it is advisable to include in the draft of the Information Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provisions related to such a contract, liability arising from it, and their protection.

Moreover, in accordance with the doctrine of civil legislation, civil liability for breach of obligations consists in assigning to the debtor who failed to fulfill the obligation the obligation to pay damages, penalties in favor of the creditor.

Consequently, in accordance with the general doctrine, it can be concluded that if the parties fail to fulfill or duly comply with the obligations stipulated in

the agreements in the field of information, the other party is obligated to compensate for damages and penalties.

